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Laser photoacoustic spectroscopy for trace gas sensing: from past to present

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$$S(\lambda_i) = S_i = CP(\lambda_i) N_{tot} \sum_{j=1}^n c_j \sigma_j(\lambda_i) \quad (5)$$

with λ_j being a specific wavelength. There are n gas components with j as the running index, i.e., c_j denotes the concentration of the j^{th} component and $\sigma_j(\lambda_j)$ its absorption cross section at the specific wavelength λ_j . N_{tot} is the total number density. A (possible) phase factor is not considered here. The concentration c_j of the j^{th} component can then be deduced by

$$c_j = \frac{1}{CN_{tot}} \sum_{i=1}^m [\sigma_j(\lambda_i)]^{-1} \left(\frac{S(\lambda_i)}{P(\lambda_i)} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $[\sigma_j(\lambda_i)]^{-1}$ is the inverse of the matrix $[\sigma_j(\lambda_i)]$.

The nature of the matrix $[\sigma_j(\lambda_i)]$ determines the effectiveness of deriving the individual gas concentrations in a multi-component mixture by Eq. (6). In the ideal case the matrix is diagonal, i.e., a set of wavelengths λ_i can be found with absorption of only one component at each λ_i . However, in the normal case, the absorption spectra of individual components overlap and interfere with each other and it is not straightforward to discriminate among the various known compounds and/or to even identify any unexpected compounds in a mixture. Using fitting procedures like principal component regression, partial least squares, a Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, a mix-match algorithm or several other approaches that have been developed in the past [3], measured spectra are in practice fitted with spectra from databases such as HITRAN [5] or the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory database [6] which contains more than 300 molecular spectra, to finally evaluate multi-component spectra and determine concentrations of individual compounds. It should be emphasized, however, that despite sophisticated data analyses, interfering absorptions can still somewhat increase the minimum detectable concentrations c_{min} for single gases as introduced above in Eq. (3).

3. Experimental arrangements

The first trace gas measurements using PA spectroscopy (PAS) have been performed by Viengorov in 1938 [7] and by Luft in 1943 [8]. With the advent of lasers with high spectral brightness, sensitive miniature electret microphones (as used, e.g., in hearing aids), lock-in detection and amplification, PAS underwent a renaissance. These new tools enabled trace gas detection and analysis. Pioneers of that time were Kerr and Atwood [9] as well as Kreuzer [10] who entered the ppbV (10^{-9}) concentration range.

Figure 2 shows a schematic of a typical experimental setup for trace gas detection using PAS. It includes a light source (typically a tunable laser), a chopper (or other kind of modulation scheme), eventually a lens to guide the laser beam through the cell, the PA gas cell itself equipped with one (or more) microphones M, a power meter for signal normalization and lock-in amplifier for processing the normalized microphone signal S/P. As light sources lamps, LEDs (including mid-IR LEDs), line tunable CO and CO₂ lasers, optical parametric oscillators (OPOs), difference frequency generation (DFG), later quantum cascade lasers (QCLs) and interband cascade lasers (ICLs) as well as frequency combs have been employed. Instead of mechanical chop-

Fig. 2: Typical experimental setup for photoacoustic gas measurements

pers, pulsed lasers or direct current modulation is used, particularly for semiconductor lasers.

In the field of PA cell configurations, the development of new cell designs is ongoing. Already in early times, acoustically resonant cells were constructed to benefit from a PA signal enhancement by the Q-factor of the acoustic resonance. Also multi-pass arrangements were presented to benefit from the enhancement of absorbed power within the cell. Both items were combined in a cell design shown in Figure 3 [11]. This cell also included a microphone array of 16 microphones arranged radially around the cylindrical cell body to further enhance the PA signal amplitude. The cell was operated at the first longitudinal acoustic resonance frequency of 1252 Hz with a Q-factor of 70. The Brewster windows and gas in- and outlets are located at pressure nodes of the first longitudinal resonance thereby minimizing both window heating and gas flow noise (up to 1.5 l/min flow rate). The number of beam passes is 36 resulting in a total beam pathlength of 23.68 m. A typical application of this cell is discussed below in the section *Applications*.

Fig. 3: Multipass resonant photoacoustic cell, equipped with a radial array of 16 microphones [11].

Numerous PA cell geometries have been presented throughout the time. An example is a multifunctional cell reported by Liu et al. [12]. The cell is equipped with three separate acoustic resonators combined in a single device. These resonators have different lengths and thus operate at different resonance frequencies. Three near-IR distributed feedback diode lasers operating at 1396 nm, 1653 nm, and 2004 nm have been used for the detection of water vapor, methane (CH₄) and CO₂, respectively. The entire cylindrical cell (including buffer volumes) measures 22 cm in length with a diameter of only 5 cm. Minimum detection limits of 0.2 ppm for CH₄ (with 400 s integration time), 12 ppm for CO₂ and 0.1 ppm for water vapor (with 100 s integration time each) could be achieved corresponding to NNEA values of a few times $10^{-9} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ W Hz}^{-1/2}$. This unique cell geometry significantly reduces the size for multi-laser PAS for multi-pollutant analysis.

Recently, 3D printed PA cells have been introduced by various authors. Bauer et al. [13] presented this new methodology for the construction of a miniaturized polymer-based resonant PA cell. The inner acoustic cylindrical resonator has a length of only 10 mm and a diameter of 1.8 mm. On each side of the cylinder, two buffer volumes of $\lambda_{ac}/4$ are added (λ_{ac} being the wavelength of the acoustic resonant wave (1st longitudinal mode)) in order to reduce the gas flow noise. A MEMS microphone is employed to record the PA signal. A near-IR diode laser at 1582 nm wavelength was used to determine acetylene (C₂H₂) with a minimum detectable concentration of 750 ppbV (SNR = 3) for a 35-s averaging time and an average laser power of 22 mW.

Most recently, Zhang et al. [14] presented a special type of a so-called differential Helmholtz PA cell. Its geometry is illustrated in Figure 4. The cell consists of two cavities separated by a tube. The laser beam passes through one cavity in a multi-pass configuration, realized by retro reflectors. Each of the two cavities is equipped with a microphone. Microphone 1 records the actual gas absorption-related PA signal while microphone 2 only records any noise (with opposite sign). The cell was tested with acetylene (C₂H₂) as probe gas at a laser wavelength of 1.53 μ m. Although not at its fundamental strong absorption a minimum detection limit of 14 ppb at an (enhanced) laser power of 1 W and 400 s averaging time was achieved.

More applications of conventional PAS studies are presented below.

Fig. 4: Setup of PAS sensor with multi-pass-retro-reflection-enhanced Differential Helmholtz PA cell and distributed-feedback (DFB) diode laser excitation with erbium-doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) [14].

A completely different novel approach to (conventional) PAS gas detection named quartz-enhanced PAS (QEPAS) has been pioneered by Kosterev et al. [15]. It uses a quartz tuning fork (QTF, as employed in watches) as sensing element instead of the conventional PA cell equipped with one or more microphones, and operates at the high QTF resonance frequency of typically 32.8 kHz with an unusual high

Q-factor of ca. 20'000. The QTF can be used in open space as a miniature sensor, but is often equipped with a tiny microresonator in the form of a sound tube to enhance the signal, as illustrated in Figure 5. Unlike in conventional PAS, the laser energy is not accumulated in the gas but rather in the QTF. This permits an energy accumulation time of typically 300 ms, considerably longer than in conventional PAS. Furthermore, the mode of the resonance frequency at 2¹⁵ Hz (\approx 32.768 kHz) corresponds to a symmetric vibration where the prongs of the QTF move in opposite directions, while the antisymmetric vibration is piezoelectrically inactive. This offers the benefit that ambient noise does not generate a signal. However, the high resonance frequency requires special attention, particularly for gas pressure-dependent measurements and for multi-species detection, as the condition (ii) mentioned above, i.e., that the nonradiative molecular relaxation time τ_{nr} is longer than the modulation cycle, may not be fulfilled any more. Furthermore, unlike in conventional PAS with a cell, a good laser beam quality is required for QEPAS as the space between the forks of the QTF is narrow (0.2 - 0.3 mm). Emphasis has thus been put into new QEPAS developments which include a novel customized clamp-type QTF which proves advantageous for lasers with poor beam quality while maintaining the high Q-factor of $> 10^4$ [16]. In the meantime QEPAS has been commercialized by CDP Systems Corp. (Moscow) and Thorlabs, Inc. (Newton, USA). Further QEPAS applications are discussed below.

Fig. 5: Optical configuration for QEPAS detection with a quartz tuning fork (QTF) [15]:

- (a) Laser beam perpendicular to the QTF plane (usual configuration).
- (b) Laser beam in the QTF plane.
- (c) An acoustic microresonator is added to enhance the signal.

A further approach named cantilever-enhanced PAS (CEPAS) differs from both conventional PAS and QEPAS as it still uses a PA cell but a cantilever as pressure sensor instead of a microphone, MEMS or QTF. The configuration is illustrated in Figure 6 [17]. The movement of a thin (\approx 5 - 10 μ m thick) silicon cantilever is measured interferometrically with a diode laser. This way, displacements well under 1 pm up to mm can be detected. In the meantime, the method has been commercialized by Gasera Ltd., Turku, Finland, and successfully been applied in various applications. The reported detection sensitivities are comparable or even better than those achieved with PAS and QEPAS measure-

Fig. 6: Setup for cantilever-enhanced PAS (CEPAS). Instead of a microphone a cantilever is used whose movement is recorded interferometrically [17].

ments. As example, in an experiment with a QCL at $5.64 \mu\text{m}$ with a power of 47 mW a detection limit for formaldehyde (CH_2O) of around 1.5 ppb (SNR = 3) in a non-resonant operation of the CEPAS systems was reported, corresponding to a NNEA coefficient of $6.5 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Wcm}^{-1}\text{Hz}^{-1/2}$ which was claimed one order of magnitude better than realized with previous PA systems [18]. More recent CEPAS applications are discussed below.

4. Applications

Most PAS, QEPAS and CEPAS studies focus on novel devices, high sensitivity, etc. generally performed in a well-controlled laboratory environment. As example, an ultrahigh sensitivity was very recently reported for a carbon monoxide (CO) and nitrous oxide (N_2O) detection, namely sub-ppt concentrations, achieved with a doubly resonant PA cell and a QCL around $4.57 \mu\text{m}$ wavelength [19]. However, there are only few true field studies.

As a representative early example of PA trace gas monitoring in ambient air a mobile CO_2 laser-based PA system is presented which was installed in a trailer and employed in a street tunnel study [20]. The focus was on the continuous monitoring of CO_2 , ethene/ethylene (C_2H_4) and ammonia (NH_3) emissions alongside a dual-lane highway at the exit of the "Gubrist" street tunnel near Zürich. A Teflon tube sucked the air 15 m inside the tunnel near the wall and flowed the air continuously at a flow rate of 0.5 l/min through the multi-pass PA cell described above and shown in Fig. 3. A photo of the trailer and a view inside are displayed in Figure 7. Both a $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ and a $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ laser were used side by side, both sealed off and automatically and consecutively set at selected laser transitions, i.e. at wavelengths characteristic for strong C_2H_4 and NH_3 absorptions, respectively, and minimum spectral

Fig. 7: Autonomous CO_2 -laser photoacoustic system in a trailer: (a) Trailer located besides dual-lane highway at tunnel exit. (b) Inside view of trailer with two CO_2 lasers in the foreground and PA cell in the background.

interferences, notably by CO_2 and H_2O vapor, for selectively detecting C_2H_4 and NH_3 . The CO_2 concentration was recorded with an independent device. The system was calibrated with certified gas mixtures before actual gas measurements were taken. For the measurement campaigns, the beams of the $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ and a $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ laser were alternatively directed through the PA cell via a computer-controlled flipper mirror. A time resolution of typically 1 min for a single measurement of one gas was achieved. The results of a 1-week measurement campaign of the three gases C_2H_4 , NH_3 and CO_2 are plotted in Figure 8. In addition the traffic count is shown at the bottom. There is obviously a good correlation with traffic counts and gas concentration peaks. The concentration fluctuations are true variations due to the excellent time resolution. All concentrations are above the background concentrations and well above the individual detection limits. It should be noted that this is one of the few studies employing a computer-controlled and totally stand-alone system.

Another example of a true field PAS study concerns aircraft measurements of C_2H_4 from industrial sources near Houston, Texas (USA). Again, a CO_2 laser was used and concentration fluctuations in the low ppb-range of ethene (C_2H_4) during flights of typical 1 hour were recorded yielding good agreement with gas chromatographic measurements on air samples collected during the flight [21].

Fig. 8: Temporal development of ammonia (NH_3), ethene (C_2H_4), CO_2 and traffic counts per 10 min (from top to bottom) during one week [20].

A further aircraft PA study was reported by Bozoki [22] who realized a diode-based near-IR PA system for the simultaneous recording of the atmospheric water vapor and total water concentration. This is a good example for the practicability, robustness and long-term reliability of the PA method which results from the proper selection of the hardware components and the development and application of self-checking and self-correcting algorithms in order to optimize the system performance before deployment and to warrant an optimized operation throughout airborne measurements.

In a recent QEPAS application, a system was realized that contains three QCLs operated at three different wavelengths for detecting ammonia (NH₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and sulphur dioxide (SO₂) under well controlled humidity conditions (in order to take the strong influence of water vapor on τ_{nr} into account [23]). Minimum detectable concentrations of 2.4 ppb (NH₃), 9 ppb (NO₂) and 9.3 ppb (SO₂), well below their abundance in air for all pollutants, were reported for an averaging time of only 0.1 s.

CEPAS applications have increased since their introduction in 2003. The first combination of CEPAS with a frequency comb has been realized by Sadiék et al. in 2018 [24]. Such an arrangement combines the broad spectral range and high spectral resolution of frequency combs with the small sample volume of CEPAS.

In a more recent study an exceptionally high detection sensitivity has been reported for hydrogen fluoride (HF). A continuous-wave (CW) optical parametric oscillator (OPO) with a power of 950 mW, tuned to a strong HF absorption line at 2476 nm, was employed. It should be noted that during a 15 s gas exchange cycle the gas cell was always closed for 6 s to record the PA signal. In this configuration a detection limit of 2.5 ppt was achieved [25]. However, the restriction of a closed cell, i.e., without flowing gas, may impede continuous *in situ* measurements.

A most recent CEPAS measurement has been performed on tritiated water (HTO) in the gas phase [26]. Since the CEPAS method offers high sensitivity in a small sample volume (11 ml in this case), it is particularly suited when working with radioactive samples. A QCL emitting at $\approx 7.32 \mu\text{m}$ was employed and directed through the PAS cell. The actual measurement was performed in a sample-and-hold configuration, i.e. a sample was transferred to the cell from a continuous by-pass flow and the cell valves were then closed during the spectral measurement. A water sample with enriched amount of HTO was used. Time series measurements with varying water and HTO concentrations were carried out. The sample in the cell was renewed every 60 s, the measurement itself (in stop-flow mode) was performed for 30 s. A HTO detection limit of 0.88 ppb for SNR = 1 and 60 s measurement time is claimed.

5. Conclusions

Photoacoustic spectroscopy has not lost its timeliness but has instead entered various fields and has experienced numerous new developments and applications. In trace gas sensing, it offers several benefits compared to other conventional yet also to other optical techniques: it is a robust and rather simple method, easy to implement, requires neither sophisticated alignment nor special optics and represents a rather low-cost sensor. Furthermore, it offers high sensitivity and a high specificity (particularly important for multi-species samples) can be achieved with an appropriate narrowband tunable laser source. Applications range from selective detection of single species in a controlled environment in the lab to field experiments (on the ground or even including airborne systems) for ambient air monitoring, to industrial process monitoring or explosives detection and also include biological and medical areas, e.g., breath monitoring for disease diagnostics.

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